

Notes on the Nycteribiidae (Diptera) of Russia

GENELINA V. FARAFONOVA

Farafonova, G. V. 2013. Notes on the Nycteribiidae (Diptera) of Russia. *Int. J. Dipterol. Res.*, 24(1): 7–11.

The first checklist of Nycteribiidae from Russia including 18 species of 4 genera is provided.

G.V. Farafonova, Department of Entomology, Biological Faculty of Moscow State University, Vorob'evy gory, Moscow, Russia, 119899 GSP Moscow V 234

Key words. Diptera, Nycteribiidae, fauna, Russia.

Introduction

The flies Nycteribiidae are known to be parasites of the bats (order Chiroptera) only. About 300 species and subspecies are divided into subfamilies — Nycteribiinae, parasites of bats (Microchiroptera) and Cyclopodinae, parasites of flying foxes (Megachiroptera). The Nycteribiidae is a typical Old World family, only representatives of 2 genera (~ 25 species) are known from Nearctic region.

All these flies are completely wingless. The nycteribiids often have a high degree of host specificity and their species diversity depends on the diversity of fauna of the bats. The fauna of Nycteribiidae of Old World is studied well and relatively full species checklists are provided in literature. However, the faunistic list of nycteribiids of Russia is absent up to date. The present paper include various materials on the Nycteribiidae from different regions of Russia.

Checklist of Nycteribiidae of Russia

Genus *Nycteribia* Latreille, 1797

N. allotopa Speiser, 1901

Material. 1 ♂, 1 ♀, **Russia**, from *Miniopterus schreibersi*, Far East, Primorsky Terr., Chasan, sugarloaf Zaozernaya, 2.08.1988, leg. P. Morozov.

Distribution. Russia: Far East. Japan, China, Ceylon, India, Burma on *M. schreibersi*.

Previous records. Medvedev et al., 1991; Farafonova, 1999.

N. formosana (Karaman, 1939)

Material. 4 ♂, 2 ♀, **Russia**, no host, Far East, Chasan, 6.07.1966, leg. V. G. Belyaev; 2 ♂, 2 ♀ from *Miniopterus schreibersi*, Far East, Chasan, sugarloaf Zaozernaya, 2.08.1981, leg. P. Morozov; 3 ♂, 3 ♀ from *Myotis capaccini*, Far East, cave Seraphimovskaya, 5.06.1983, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♂, 1 ♀ from

M. daubentoni, Far East, cave Velican, 11.03.1983, leg. M. Tiunov; 2 ♀ from *Plecotus auritus*, Far East, cave Bogataya Fanza, 7.03.1983, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♀, from *M. cappacini*, Far East, cave Velican, 11.03.1983, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 2 ♀, from *M. daubentoni*, Far East, cave Letuchaya mish, 14.06.1985, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 5 ♂, 4 ♀, from *M. cappacini*, Far East, Chasan, sugarloaf Zaozernaya, 18.07.1985, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♂, from *M. cappacini*, Sachalinskaya ar., Kunashir, 2.08.1985, leg. M. P. Tiunov.

Distribution. Russia: Far East. China, Taiwan (Formosa), Japan (?) on *Miniopterus schreibersi*, *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*, *Myotis ricketti*.

Previous records. Medvedev et al., 1991; Farafonova, 1999.

N. kolenati Theodor et Moscona, 1954

Material. 16 ♂, 20 ♀, **Russia**, from *Vespertilio* sp., Simbirskaya reg. (Ul'ynovskaya obl.) 07/1896, leg. Pleske, det. Stakelberg; 9 ♂, 14 ♀, from *Myotis daubentoni*, Penzensk Distr., Novo-Lomovsky rest., vill. Virta, -09.1983, leg. V. Yu. Il'in; 1 ♂, from *M. brandti* *ibid.*, 13.12.1977, leg. V. Yu. Il'in; 5 ♀, from *M. daubentoni*, Penza, Norovschatsk Distr., vill. Skan, -08.1983, leg. V. Yu. Il'in; 6 ♂, 6 ♀, from *M. daubentoni*, Krasnodarsk Terr., Adlersky Distr., -08.1999, leg. A. Borisenko. Pscov Prov., 2 ♂, 3 ♀, from *Myotis dasycneme*, -04.1984, leg. Masing.

Distribution. European part of Russia and Ural. Caucasus, Kazakhstan on *Myotis daubentoni*, *M. nattereri*, *Vespertilio murinus*, *Eptesicus serotinus*.

Previous records. Markova, 1938; Orlova, 2011.

N. latreillii (Leach, 1817)

Material. 1 ♂, **Russia**, Northern Osetiya, Alagir, 13.06.1982, from *M. blythi*, leg. S. Alekseev; 6 ♂, 6 ♀, from *M. daubentoni*, Krasnodarsky Terr., Adler Prov., caves, -08.1999, leg. A. Borisenko.

Distribution. South Russia. Continental Europe, North Africa, West Asia on *Myotis myotis*, *M. blythi*, *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*.

N. pedicularia Latreille, 1805

Material. 1 ♂, 2 ♀, **Russia**, Altai, cave, -08.1989, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. A. Polcanov; 1 ♂, 4 ♀, Adygea, -07.1985, from *Miniopterus schreibersi*, leg. S. Alekseev.

Distribution. Russia: North Caucasus, Altai. Continental Europe, North Africa, West Asia on *Miniopterus schreibersi*, *Myotis myotis*, *M. cappacini*, *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*.

N. pygmaea (Kishida, 1932)

Material. 5 ♂, 4 ♀, **Russia**, Magadansk Prov., Ol'sk distr., riv. Shelomdga, -08.1981, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. M. E. Dokushaev; 2 ♂, 1 ♀, 14.08.1982, from *M. daubentoni* *ibid.*, leg. M. Dokushaev; 75 ♂, 108 ♀, no host, Far East, Chasan, -07.1966, leg. Belyaev; 1 ♂, Far East, Chasan, sugarloaf Zaozernaya, 2.08.1981, from *Miniopterus schreibersi*, leg. P. Morosov.

Distribution. Russia: Far East. Japan, Korea on *Rhinolophus ferrumequinus*, *Myotis* sp., *Pipistrellus savii*.

Previous records. Medvedev et al, 1991; Farafonova, 1999.

N. quasiocellata Theodor, 1966

Material. 15 ♂, 18 ♀, **Russia**, Novosibirsk Prov., Maslyaninsky distr., caves, 2.05.1981, from *M. daubentoni* and *M. mystacinus*, leg. P. Morozov; 1 ♂, 3 ♀, from *M. daubentoni*, Altai, cave, -03.1986, leg. A. Polcanov; 1 ♀, Chitinsk Prov., cave Kira, -07.1988, from *Eptesicus nilssoni*, leg. A. Hritankov; 1 ♂, 5 ♀, Krasnoyarsk Terr., Schugur, 1988, from *M. mystacinus*, leg. A. Hritankov; 2 ♂, 2 ♀, Krasnoyarsk Terr., cave Ledopadnaya, -03.1987, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. A. Hritankov; 2 ♂, 2 ♀, Krasnoyarsk Terr., Malaya Siya, cave Archeologycheskaya, 5.10.1989, from *M.*

daubentoni, leg. A. Hritankov; 2 ♂, Krasnoyarsk Terr., cave Torgalinskaya, 21.12.1989, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. Kotepov; 2 ♂, 3 ♀, Chabarovsk Terr., Blagoveschensk, mansarda of house, 12.06.1984, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 9 ♂, 7 ♀, Ayano-Maysky dist., caves, -08.1984, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. M. Tiunov.

Distribution. Russia: Siberia. Mongolia, East Kazakhstan, North China on *M. daubentoni*, *M. mystacinus*, *Eptesicus nilsoni*.

Previous records. Medvedev et al., 1991; Farafonova, 1999.

N. schmidlii Schiner, 1853

Material. 1 ♂, 2 ♀, **Russia**, Krasnoyarsk Terr., near Sochi, -07.1978, from *Miniopterus schreibersi*, leg. P. Sagdieva; 1 ♂, 3 ♀, Simbirskaya (U`yanovskaya) gub., -08.1896, no host, det. A. A. Schakelberg (collection Zool. Inst., St. Petersburg) leg. Pleske; 1 ♂, 4 ♀, Krasnoyarsk Terr., near Adler, cave, 19.08.1979, from *Pipistrellus* sp., leg. M. Perov.

Distribution. Russia: North Caucasus, Central Volga. Crimea, Caucasus. Austria, Turkey, Lebanon, Israel, Iran, Afghanistan, Algeria on *Miniopterus schreibersi*, *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*, *Rh. euryale*, *Plecotus auritus*.

Previous records. Stakelberg, 1970.

N. vexata Westwood, 1835

Material. 2 ♂, 3 ♀, **Russia**, Krasnoyarsk Terr., near Adler, cave, 19.08.1979, from *Myotis* sp., leg. M. Perov.

Distribution. Russia: North Caucasus. Crimea, Caucasus, West Europe, North Africa, West Asia on *Myotis oxygnathus*, *Rhinolophus* spp., *Plecotus auritus*.

Previous records. Volkova, 1957.

Genus Phthiridium Hermann 1804 *Phth. biarticulatum* (Hermann, 1804)

Material. 1 ♂, **Russia**, Krasnoyarsk Terr., caves, -08.1976, from *Rhinolophus* sp., leg. M. Perov.

Distribution. Russia: North Caucasus. Continental Europe, North Africa, West Asia on *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*, *Miniopterus schreibersi*, *Pipistrellus pipistrellus*.

Previous records. Stakelberg, 1970.

Genus Basilia Miranda-Ribeiro, 1903

B. nana Theodor, 1954

Material. 1 ♂, 4 ♀, **Russia**, Krasnoyarsk Terr., near Adler, caves, -08.1999, from *Myotis bechsteini*, leg. A. Borisenko; 1 ♀, Caucasus State Natur Reserve, Laura, -07.1999, from *M. mystacinus*, leg. A. Borisenko.

Distribution. Russia: North Caucasus. Europe, Caucasus, Israil on *M. bechsteini*, *M. dasycneme*, *M. nattereri*.

B. rybini Hurka, 1969

Material. 6 ♂, 7 ♀, **Russia**, Novosibirsk Prov., Maslyaninsk dist., caves, 2.05.1981, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. P. Morozov; 2 ♂, 2 ♀, Far East, Primorsky Terr., cave Seraphimovskaya, 4.02.1983, from *M. nattereri*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♂, Far East, Primorsky Terr., cave Makrushinskaya, 6.02.1983, from *M. nattereri*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♂, Far East, Primorsky Terr., cave Velican, 11.03.1983, from *M. frater*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Primorsky Terr., cave Priiskovaya, 13.02.1983, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♂, Primorsky Terr., Chasan, -03.1983, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♀, Chabarovsk Terr., 18.08.1983, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♀, Chabarovsk Terr., 27.08.1983, from *M. frater*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♂, 4 ♀, Chabarovsk Terr., cave Sary Medved, from *M. nattereri*; 5 ♂, 4 ♀, Altai, caves, 25.01-5.02.1989, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. A. Polkanov.

Distribution. Russia: Siberia, Far East. Kazakhstan, Turkmenia, Far East on *M. daubentoni*, *M. mystacinus*.

Previous records. Medvedev et al., 1991; Farafonova, 1999.

B. truncata Theodor, 1966

Material. 1 ♂, 2 ♀, Far East, Chasan, sugarloaf Zaozernaya, -08.1981, from *Miniopterus schreibersi*, leg. P. Morozov; 1 ♂, Far East, cave Priiskovaya, 17.12.1983, from *Murina leucogaster*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♀, Far East, Kiparisovo, 25.07.1985, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 2 ♂, Chabarovsk Terr., cave Steregushee Kop'e, 24.10.1983, from *M. brandti*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 2 ♂, 2 ♀, Chabarovsk Terr., cave, Proshania, 30.10.1983, from *M. brandti*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 2 ♂, 7 ♀, Chabarovsk Terr., cave Sary medved', 30.10.1983, from *M. brandti*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♂, Altay, cave, 5.02.1983, from *Murina leucogaster*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 2 ♂, 4 ♀, Chakasia, caves, 1986, from *M. brandti*, leg. A. Hritankov; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Krasnoyarsk Terr., cave Ledopadnaya, 22.03.1987, from *M. brandti*, leg. A. Hritankov; 2 ♂, 2 ♀, from *M. daubentoni*, Krasnoyarsk Terr., cave Tergalinskaya, 21.12.1989, leg. Kotepov; 1 ♂, from *M. brandti*, Krasnoyarsk Terr., cave Podnebesnaya, -02.1984, leg. A. Hritankov.

Distribution. Russia: Far East, Siberia. Mongolia on *M. mystacinus*, *M. daubentoni*.

Previous records. Medvedev et al., Farafonova, 1999.

B. truncatiformis Farafonova, 1998

Material. 2 ♂, 3 ♀, Russia, Krasnoyarsk Terr., Shirinsk dist., vill. Malaya Siya, cave Archeologicheskaya, 5.10.1989, from *M. brandti*, leg. A. Hritankov, Denisova; 2 ♂, 1 ♀, Krasnoyarsk Terr., river Biryusa, caves, 19.09.1989, from *M. brandti*, leg. A. Hritankov.

Distribution. Russia: Siberia on *M. brandti*.

Previous records. Farafonova, 1998.

Genus *Penicillidia* Kolenati, 1863***P. conspicua* Speiser, 1901**

Material. 1 ♂, Russia, from *Vesperugo* sp., Simbirskaya gub., 12.08.1896, leg. Pleske, det. A. Stakelberg.

Distribution. Russia: Central Volga, Tatarstan, Zabaikal'e. Europe, North Africa. On

Miniopterus schreibersi, *Myotis* spp., *Rhinolophus* sp.

Previous records. Volkova, 1957; Jovty et al., 1962; Stakelberg, 1970.

***P. dufouri* Westwood, 1835**

Material. 1 ♀, Russia, Simbirskaya gub., 12.08.1896, no host, leg. Pleske, det. Stakelberg; 1 ♂, Novosibirsk Prov., caves, 2.05.1981, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. P. Morozov; 1 ♂, Penzensk Prov., Novo-Lomovsky dist., vill. Virga, 11.07.1983, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. V. Yu. Il'in; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Kalininsk Prov., cave, 1985, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. K. K. Panyutin; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Altai, -02.1989, from *M. dasyncneme*, leg. A. Polcanov.

Distribution. Russia: European part, West Siberia. Europe, North Africa, West Asia to the Himalayas on *Myotis* spp., *Rhinolophus* spp., *Miniopterus schreibersi*.

Previous records. Stakelberg, 1970; Medvedev et al., 1991.

***P. jenynsii* (Westwood, 1835)**

Material. 2 ♂, Russia, Far East, Chasan, 7.07.1966, from *Miniopterus schreibersi*, leg. V. G. Belyaev, 2 ♂, 4 ♀, Far East, Chasan, sugarloaf Zaozernaya, 26.07.1981, from *M. schreibersi*, leg. P. Morozov; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, 2.08.1981, from *M. schreibersi*, *ibid.* leg. P. Morozov.

Distribution. Russia: Far East. China, Japan, Taiwan on *Miniopterus schreibersi*.

Previous records. Medvedev et al., 1991.

***P. monoceros* Speiser, 1900**

Material. 2 ♂, 1 ♀, Russia, Novosibirsk Prov., cave, 2.05.1981, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. P. Morozov; 4 ♀, Altai, 25.01-5.02.1989, from *M. daubentoni*, leg. A. Polcanov; 2 ♂, 1 ♀, Far East, Primorsk Terr., cave Sinegorskaya, 6.11.1983, from *M. nattereri*, leg. M. Tiunov; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Far East, Primorsk Terr., cave Seraphimovskaya, 4.02.1983, from *M. nattereri*, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 1 ♀, Chabarovsk Terr., Ayano-Maisky dist., Abogy-Dyus, 13.08.1984, from

M. daubentoni, leg. M. P. Tiunov; 2 ♂, 4 ♀, Kalininsk Prov., quarry, 28.03.1985, from *M. dasyncneme*, leg. P. Morozov.

Distribution. Russia: European part, Siberia, Far East. Mongolia on *M. daubentoni*, *M. dasyncneme*, *Plecotus auritus*, *Eptesicus nilssoni*.

Previous records. Markova, 1938; Stakelberg, 1970; Medvedev et al., 1991.

Discussion

Thus, a total of 18 species (genera *Nycteribia*, *Phthiridium*, *Basilia* and *Penicillidia*) of subfamily Nycteribiinae are found in Russia, it is more than half of 32 species of this subfamily known from Palaearctic. We found 8 nycteribiid species in the Far East, 7 species in Siberia, 7 species in the south of European Russia and 4 species in the center of European Russia.

References

- Volkova, L. I. 1957. Bloodsucking flies of Tatar and Chuvash Republics. *Scientific notes of Kazan State University*, **117**(2): 241–245. (In Russian)
- Jovty, I. F., Zarubina, V. N., Prokopen, V. N., Schvedko L. P. 1962. Ectoparasites of the bats in the South-Eastern Transbaikalia and adjacent areas in Mongolia. *News of Irkutsk state research Institute of the plague struggle of Siberia and the Far East*, **24**: 338–343. (In Russian)
- Markova, L. I. 1938. Influence of winter hibernation on parasitofauna of bats. *Zool. J.*, **17**: 133–145. (In Russian)
- Medvedev, S. G., Stanukovith, M. K., Tiunov, M. P., Farafonova, G. V. 1991. Ectoparasites of bats from the Far East. *Parasitology*, **25**(1): 27–37. (In Russian)
- Orlova, M. V. 2011. Ectoparasites of the pond bat (*Myotis dasyncneme* (Boie, 1825), Chiroptera) in the Urals. *Materials of scientific conference of the Fundamental problems of entomology in the XXI century*: 123.
- Farafonova, G. V. 1998. New species of Nycteribiid flies of the genus *Basilia* Miranda Ribeiro, 1903 (Diptera, Nycteribiidae). *Entomol. Rev.*, **77**(1): 224–228.
- Farafonova, G. V. 1999. Family Nycteribiidae. *Key to the insects of Russian Far East*, Diptera and Siphonaptera, **VI**(1): 581–588. (In Russian)
- Stakelberg, A. A. 1970. Fam. Nycteridiidae. Key to the insects of European part USSR. V. Diptera and Siphonaptera, **V**(2): 603–607. (In Russian)

Received 28.1.2013